

GuidelinesClaudinha

Brazilian Data Protection Law (EN)

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v. 3.0

VERSION HISTORY

Version	Validity	Changes	Responsible
V0	09/2021 - 02/2022	- Initial version.	Ananda, Felipe, Guilherme, Igor, Jéssica, Prof. Jaime Sichman, Prof. Juliano Maranhão, Prof. Roberto Pfeiffer, Raphael.
V1	02/2022 - 06/2022	- Review of V0; - Exclusion of the tags indicated in “History of Deleted Tags”; - Addition of tags in the First PPD Block, specifying the holder's rights; - Aggregation of tags in the Second PPD Block; - Changes to the Third PPD Block.	Felipe, Igor, Jessica, Raphael
V2	06/2022	- Formatting changes; - Creation of the topic “History of Deleted Tags”; - Update of the summary.	Igor, Jessica
V3	07/2022	- Deletion of the 'Controller Contact' tag to join with the 'Controller ID' tag - Deletion of the 'Treatment Hypotheses' tag - Unification of the tags “generic expressions” and “non-specific quantifiers” - Deletion of the tags “Substantial treatment information” and “Concision” - Deletion of the 'personal data processing' tag	Felipe, Jessica.

SUMMARY

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1. Tagging instructions for Privacy Policies

The purpose of this section of the document is (i) to present the idea of tagging Privacy Policies to the Claudinha Project team and open it for comments and (ii) to provide instructions on how to undertake this task.

1.1.Types of mapped clauses

Clause type	What is it about?	Symbol
First block: Omission of data required by law		
Controller identification	Are the identification and contact information of the data controller made available in a clear, adequate and conspicuous manner?	<id>
Identity and contact of the person in charge	The identity and contact information of the Data Protection Officer are disclosed publicly in a clearly and objectively way? (preferably on the controller's website)	<dpo>
Purpose of treatment	Is the purpose of the processing made available in a clear, adequate, obvious and easily accessible way to the data subject?	<purp>
Duration of treatment	Is free and easy consultation on the form and duration of treatment guaranteed to holders?	<ret>
Right to confirm the existence of treatment	The information about the holder's right to confirm the existence of treatment and how they can exercise it is explicitly exposed?	<existence>
Right of access to data	Is the information of the holder's right to access data and how this right can be exercise it exposed in an explicit way?	<access >
Right to data correction	Is the information about the holder's right to correct incomplete, inaccurate or outdated data explicit and how can this right be exercised if it is exposed in an explicit way?	<rectification>
Right to anonymization,	Is the information explicit that the holder has the right to request anonymization, blocking or deletion of unnecessary, excessive	<anonymization >

blocking and deletion	or processed data that does not comply with the LGPD, as well as how to exercise this right?	
Right to portability	Is the information explicit that the holder has the right to request the portability of their data to another service or product provider, as well as how to exercise this right?	<portability>
Right of deletion	Is it clear that the holder has the right to request the deletion of their data processed based on consent?	<erasure>
Purpose of sharing	Does the holder have easy access to information about the shared use of data by the controller and the purpose of the processing?	<reception>
Right to information about non-consent	Is it explicitly stated that the data subject has the right to information about the option of not providing consent and the consequences of refusal, as well as how they can exercise this right	<nonconsent>
Right to revoke consent	Is the right to withdraw consent and the method for exercising this right clearly outlined in the contract?	<withdraw>
Third party sharing	Is it informed which third parties personal data is shared with?	<transfer>
Express consent	Does consent, when provided in writing, appear in a clause that stands out from the others?	<consent>
Category of processed data	What type of data is being collected and processed? (examples: location data, consumption, etc.)	<cat>
Source from which personal data was obtained	Does the clause inform the source of data obtained indirectly by the controller or operator?	<source>
Automated decision	Does the clause inform the way in which automated decisions are made? If so, does it inform the right of review and its exercise?	<auto>
Second block: Clauses on data processing		
Consent by use	Is consent given merely by use?	<cuse>

“Take it or leave it” approach	Is the use of services conditional on acceptance of data processing?	<tol>
Policy changes	Are changes to privacy policies properly informed to the data subject?	<pch>
Data processing of children and adolescents	Is consent from children’s legal guardians obtained and verified?	<child>
Advertising	Is consent necessary for processing for advertising purposes? Is opt-out possible?	<ad>
Any other type of consent	Are there “hidden” consents?	<c>
Use of Cookies	Is there an explanation about the collection of cookies?	<cookie>
Third block: Use of unclear language		
Generic expressions	Generic expressions, abstract actions and activities in unclear contexts, such as "generally", "normally", "to a large extent", "often", "may be used", "it is possible that", etc.	<eg>
General Clauses		
Any other type of clause that we believe to be particularly problematic	Note a clause that may potentially be problematic, but is not included in any of the Guideline tags.	<out>
Deleted clauses		
Right to petition	Does the clause inform the right to petition the ANPD?	<complain>

Holder's rights	Are the holder's rights and how to exercise them specified? (e.g. right to access data, correction, anonymization, etc.)	<correct>
Responsibilities of processing agents	Do the clauses inform, in a specific, adequate and clear way, the responsibilities of the processing agents?	<resp>
Treatment hypotheses	Is the hypothesis on which the treatment is based highlighted in the contract?	<basis>
International Data Transfer	How are international data transfer mechanisms described?	<cross>
Data licensing	[Awaiting response]	<lic>
Communications Confidentiality	What is the degree of confidentiality regarding any communications carried out by the service?	<msg>
Transfers to third parties	Situations in which the involvement of third parties in data processing is anticipated.	<tp>
Processing of sensitive personal data	Are the clauses in accordance with legal provisions on the processing of sensitive personal data?	<sens>
Indeterminate conditioners	Phrases or terms that create a dependency of an action or activity on an uncertain event, such as "as necessary", "from time to time", etc.	<con>
Modulation	Non-specific adverbs and adjectives, which create uncertainty regarding the possibility of certain actions and events occurring.	<mo>
Treatment modality	The controller fails to indicate the specific methods of data processing (noting processes, means and purposes of processing).	<met>

Substantial treatment information	There is no significant information about the logic used, as well as the importance and expected consequences of the processing for the data subject.	<ist>
Conciseness	The clause provides information that is not very concise and unjustifiably long texts are used, which make the meaning of the clause unclear	<cc>

1.2.Degrees of abusiveness

An unfair clause must be understood as a contractual clause not individually negotiated which, contrary to the requirement of good faith, causes a significant imbalance in the rights and obligations of the parties arising from the contract, to the detriment of the consumer. As you can see, this is a very general principle. It is complemented by the annex, which, however, only contains a list of potentially abusive clauses (e.g. reversal of the burden of proof). The instructions below may be based on various sources - mainly court decisions - which, however, do not provide answers to all questions.

For each block below, we proposed a different gradation:

- (i) For the first block, which deals with necessary information required by law, we determined a binary gradation between “1”, for Completely Informative, and “3”, for Insufficiently Informative. In this sense, failure to comply with any of the necessary requirements makes it Insufficiently Informative. It is worth highlighting that, in the Claudette project, there was no gradation to complete omission as machine learning techniques were used to detect these omissions;
- (ii) For the second block, which deals with clauses regarding the processing of personal data itself, the gradation of treatment indicated by the clause is threefold: “1”, for fair treatment, in which the clause meets all legal requirements and does not have abusive content, “2”, for potentially unfair, and “3”, for unfair; It is
- (iii) For the third block, which deals with the use of unclear language in the analyzed clauses, the classification also has a triple gradation: “1”, for clauses without problems of interpretation, “2” for potentially problematic clauses and “3” for clauses clearly problematic.

For example:

- <lc1> Clause containing indeterminate conditioners that is fair </ci1>

- <eg2> Clause containing potentially unfair generic expressions. </eg2>

- <mo3> Clause with clearly unfair modulation. </mo3>

We also discussed how necessary the presence of a certain clause is for its analysis. This degree of necessity is, therefore, defined as “YES” when the presence is, in fact, necessary or “NO”, when abusiveness is detected by the absence of mention of any contractual term or provision.

Clause type	Need for Express Presence in the text	Degree of abusiveness	Conditions	Example	Observations/Justifications
First block: Omission of data provided for by law					
Controller identification	YES, based on art. 9th, III, of the LGPD	1	The identification of the data controller is made available in a clear and complete manner.	<p><id1> >If you use our services in the United States, Uber Technologies, Inc. is the data controller for your information.</id1></p> <p><id1> If you use our services in the European Union or elsewhere, Uber B.V. is the data controller. </id1></p>	The above clause is fully informative concerning the identity of the controller.
		2	<i>Not applicable</i>	-	-
		3	The identification of the data controller is vague or insufficient. An example of this is a clause that indicates to the data subject that they must check their email or invoice to access information about the controller. Likewise, a clause that only allows the identification of the controller through inferences is also insufficiently informative, as it does not observe a standard of clarity and accessibility.	<p><id3> Your Netflix service provider and data controller depends on your country of membership, and will be listed in your membership or payment confirmation email </id3></p>	The above clause fails to be fully informative since it fails to provide the data subject with easily accessible information on the data controller: to identify the controller, the data subject is supposed to check in the membership or payment confirmation email, presumably received by the data subject after having already given his or her consent and concluded the contract. As noted in WP29 Guidelines on Transparency, the requirement that the provision of information to, and the communication with, data subjects should be done in an

easily accessible manner means that the data subject should not have to seek out the information; it should be immediately apparent to them where and how the information can be accessed, for example by providing it directly to them or by linking them to it. Thus, this clause undoubtedly represents a low standard for the clarity and accessibility of the information.

The Claudette group did not identify an example of a clause that fully meets the criterion.

The clause above fails to be fully informative since it generically refers to the possibility of contacting the DPO but does not provide the DPO name and a postal address, only a link to an online form. Thus, it only reaches a low

Identity and contact of the person in charge	It is desirable that YES. However, the LGPD states that the identity and contact information, preferably, should be made available on the controller's website (art. 41, 1°, LGPD)	1	The clause includes the name of the person in charge, a mailing address, a telephone number and/or an email address specific to the holders, and, when appropriate, for the purposes of communicating with the public, other means of communication, such as a dedicated hotline, or a dedicated contact form addressed to the incumbent on the organization's website.	<dpo1> (...) </dpo1>	
		2	<i>Not applicable</i>	-	-
		3	Any other case that does not comply with the above, that is, does not include the name of the person in charge, a mailing address, a telephone number and/or an email address, and,	<dpo3> Contact the Data Protection Officer for Facebook Ireland Ltd </dpo3> <dpo3> >You may exercise any of the rights described in this section before your applicable Airbnb Data Controller and Payments Data	

			when appropriate, for purposes of communication with the public, other means of communication, such as a dedicated hotline, or a dedicated contact form addressed to the person in charge on the organization's website.	Controller by sending an email to dpo@airbnb.com .	standard for the clarity and accessibility of the information. The clause above fails to be fully informative since it only provides a dedicated email address, omitting both the name of the DPO and a postal address. Thus, it only reaches a low standard for the clarity and accessibility of the information.
Purpose of treatment	YES, based on art. 9th, I, of the LGPD	1	These are the clauses that specifically and clearly inform the purposes of data processing.	<purp1> If you are a Host, the Payments Data Controller may require identity verification information (such as images of your government issued ID, passport, national ID card, or driving license) or other authentication information, your date of birth, your address, email address, phone number and other information in order to verify your identity, provide the Payment Services to you, and to comply with applicable law </purp1>	The above clause is fully informative since it clearly specifies the purposes of the processing with regard to specific data or categories of data and it is clear how the collected data helps to verify the data subject identity and to provide the payment services.
		2	<i>Not applicable</i>	-	-
		3	Clauses that are not exhaustive and/or are vague regarding the purpose of the processing (e.g. when a clause only provides examples)	<purp3> WhatsApp must receive or collect some information to operate, provide, improve, understand, customize, support, and market our Services, including when you install, access, or use our Services </purp3>	The clause above fails to be fully informative since it generically refers to "some information" and it is vague as to the purposes of the processing. In particular, it is unclear (i) what type of data will be processed; (ii) what is the correlation between the collected information and the specific purposes, since the clause only lists a number of

different purposes one after the other (iii) what “improve” “customize”, “understand”, “support” or “market” implies, for example what kind of customization this refers to; (iii) the type of analysis which the controller is going to undertake as well as what the consequences of the processing implications

The above clause is fully informative since it clearly specifies that the data controller does not retain messages, which are deleted right after the delivery.

The above clause fails to be fully informative since it does not allow the data subject to assess, at least on the basis of his or her situation, what the retention period will be for specific data/purposes, only mentioning as a general criterion to determine this period the necessity of data for providing services and products.

Duration of treatment	YES, based on art. 9th, II, of the LGPD	1	The clause expresses that the processor will not retain personal data, or specifies the period for which the personal data will be stored, or, if it is not possible to specify the period, indicates the criteria used to determine it.	<ret1> We do not retain your messages in the ordinary course of providing our Services to you. Once your messages (including your chats, photos, videos, voice messages, files, and share location information) are delivered, they are deleted from our servers. </ret1>	
		2	<i>Not applicable</i>	-	-
		3	Clauses that generally state that personal data will be kept for as long as necessary for the legitimate purposes of processing, or written in a way that does not allow the data subject to evaluate what the retention period will be.	<ret3> We store data until it is no longer necessary to provide our services and Facebook Products, or until your account is deleted - whichever comes first. This is a case-by-case determination that depends on things like the nature of the data, why it is collected and processed, and relevant legal or operational retention needs. </ret3>	

Right to confirm the existence of treatment	YES, based on arts. 9°, VII, and 18, I, of the LGPD	1	Clauses that expressly mention the holder's right to obtain confirmation of the existence of treatment and how to exercise this right.	<existence1> The data subject has the right to confirm whether their personal data is being processed, as per Article 15 of the GDPR. Requests can be directed to the Data Protection Officer </existence1>	-
		2	<i>Not applicable.</i>	<existence2> (...) </existence2>	-
		3	Clauses that do not fit into what is described above, that is, do not explain the holder's right to confirmation of the existence of treatment and/or how he can exercise it.	<existence3> The parties agree to comply with all applicable laws regarding personal data processing under this agreement, ensuring data protection standards are upheld </existence3>	-
Right of access to data	YES, based on arts. 9°, VII, and 18, II, of the LGPD	1	Clauses that expressly mention the holder's right to access their data and how to exercise this right.	You can request access to your personal information, or correct or update out-of-date or inaccurate personal information we hold about you. You can most easily do this by visiting the "Account" portion of our website, where you have the ability to access and update a broad range of information about your account, including your contact information, your Netflix payment information, and various related information about your account (such as the content you have viewed and rated, and your reviews). You must be signed in to access the "Account" section.	You may access and update some of your information through your Account settings. If you have chosen to connect your Airbnb Account to a third party application, like Facebook or Google, you can change your settings and remove permission for the app by changing your Account settings. You are responsible for keeping your personal information up-to-date. [...] You have the right to ask us to correct inaccurate or incomplete personal information concerning you (and which you cannot update yourself within your Airbnb Account).[...] In some jurisdictions, applicable law may entitle you to request copies of your personal
		2	Clauses that do not fit into what is described above, that is, do not explain the holder's right to access data and/or how they can exercise it.		
		3	Clauses that preclude, in advance, the holder's right to access data.		

information held by us. You may also be entitled to request copies of personal information that you have provided to us in a structured, commonly used, and machine-readable format and/or request us to transmit this information to another service provider (where technically feasible).

You may access and update some of your information through your Account settings. If you have chosen to connect your Airbnb Account to a third party application, like Facebook or Google, you can change your settings and remove permission for the app by changing your Account settings. You are responsible for keeping your personal information up-to-date.[...] You have the right to ask us to correct inaccurate or incomplete personal information concerning you (and which you cannot update yourself within your Airbnb Account).[...] In some jurisdictions, applicable law may entitle you to request copies of your personal information held by us. You may also be entitled to request copies of personal information that you have provided to us in a structured,

You can request access to your personal information, or correct or update out-of-date or inaccurate personal information we hold about you. You can most easily do this by visiting the "Account" portion of our website, where you have the ability to access and update a broad range of information about your account, including your contact information, your Netflix payment information, and various related information about your account (such as the content you have viewed and rated, and your reviews). You must be signed in to access the "Account" section.

1
Clauses that expressly mention the holder's right to correct incomplete, inaccurate or outdated data, and how to exercise this right.

2
Clauses that do not explain the holder's right to correct incomplete, inaccurate or outdated data, or only make it clear in relation to one or two of these types of data, and/or how the holder can exercise this right.

3
Clauses that prohibit, in advance, the holder's right to correct incomplete, inaccurate or outdated data.

YES, based on arts. 9°, VII, and 18, III, of the LGPD

Right to correct incomplete, inaccurate or outdated data

					commonly used, and machine-readable format and/or request us to transmit this information to another service provider (where technically feasible).
Right to anonymize, block or delete unnecessary, excessive or processed data that does not comply with the LGPD	YES, based on art. 9°, VII, and 18, IV, of the LGPD	1	Clauses that expressly mention the holder's right to anonymize, block or eliminate unnecessary, excessive data or that they consider to be treated in non-compliance with the LGPD. It is necessary to explain how this right is exercised.	<anony1> The data subject has the right to request the anonymization, blocking, or deletion of unnecessary or excessive data, or data processed in non-compliance with data protection regulations. Requests should be directed to the Data Protection Office </anony1>	-
		2	<i>Not applicable</i>	-	-
		3	Clauses that do not fit into what is described above, that is, do not explain such rights, or only explain one of them, and/or fail to explain the ways in which the holder can exercise it.	<anony3> The parties agree to handle personal data in compliance with applicable laws and regulations, ensuring data protection standards are maintained. </anony3>	-
Right of portability to another service or product provider, upon express request	YES, based on art. 9°, VII, and 18, V, of the LGPD	1	Clauses that expressly mention the holder's right to request the portability of their data to another service or product provider, indicating the procedures necessary to do so (e.g.: channel to make the request, deadline, etc.)	<portability1> The data subject has the right to request the portability of their data to another service provider. To exercise this right, the data subject may submit a request through the designated channel, and the data will be transferred within the specified timeframe. </portability1>	-

		2	<i>Not applicable</i>	-	-
		3	Clauses that do not fit into what is described above, that is, do not explain the right to portability or fail to indicate the forms of exercise.	<portability3> Both parties agree to comply with legal requirements and industry standards when transferring personal data</portability3>	-
Right to delete personal data processed with the holder's consent	YES, in view on arts. 9°, VII and 18, VI, of the LGPD	1	Clauses that expressly mention the holder's right to request the deletion of data processed with their consent, except as provided in art. 16 of the LGPD, indicating the necessary procedures for this.	<erasure1> Upon request, individuals have the right to demand the deletion of their personal data that was processed with their consent. To initiate this process, individuals may submit a deletion request through the designated communication channel</erasure1>	-
		2	<i>Not applicable</i>	-	-
		3	Clauses that do not fit into what is described above, that is, they do not explain the right to delete data processed based on consent or fail to indicate how to exercise it.	<erasure3> The parties agree to comply with legal requirements and industry standards regarding the processing of personal data</erasure3>	-
Data sharing	YES, based on arts. 9°, V, and 18, VII, of the LGPD	1	The clause provides information about the recipients of personal data.	<recep1> We share information relating to our users with selected third parties who provide us with a variety of different services that support the delivery of our services (let's call them "Third Party Processors"). These Third Party Processors range from providers of technical infrastructure to customer	The above clause is fully informative, since it specifies the categories of recipients, by indicating the type and the sector, i.e. providers of technical infrastructure, customer service and authentication.

				service and authentication tools. We require any Third Party Processor which handles information on our behalf to do so pursuant to contractual terms which require that the information is kept secure, is processed in accordance with applicable data protection laws, and used only as we have instructed and not for that Third Party Processor's own purposes (unless you have explicitly consented to them doing so). </recep1>	
		2	<i>Not applicable</i>	-	
		3	Clauses that do not fit into what is described above, that is, do not provide clear information about the recipients of the data, such as whether a private or public entity, the type of industry, economic sector or location.	<recep3> At times Apple may make certain personal information available to strategic partners that work with Apple to provide products and services, or that help Apple market to customers. </recep3>	The above clause fails to be fully informative, since it is unclear the type, the industry, the sector and the location of the mentioned strategic partners.
Right to information about the possibility of not providing consent and the consequences of refusal	YES, based on arts. 9°, VII, and 18, VIII of the LGPD	1	Clauses that expressly mention both the information holder's right to the possibility of not providing consent and the consequences of such denial, and the way in which this right can be exercised.	<nonconsent1>The data subject has the explicit right to be informed about the option to refuse consent and the consequences of such refusal, as per data protection regulations. This right can be exercised by submitting a request for information through the designated contact point. The Data Protection Officer will provide clear details within a reasonable timeframe.</nonconsent1>	-

		2	<i>Not applicable</i>	-	-
		3	Clauses that do not fit into what is described above, that is, do not explain such rights, or only explain one of them, and/or fail to explain the ways in which the holder can exercise it.	<nonconsent3> The parties agree to handle consent in compliance with applicable data protection laws and standards, ensuring transparency in data processing </nonconsent3>	-
Right to revoke consent	YES, based on arts. 8th, § 5th, 9th, VII and 18, IX, of the LGPD	1	The possibility of revoking consent, when there is a legal basis for data processing, must be clear and exercised through a free procedure made easier for the holder	<withdraw1> (...) </withdraw1>	-
		2	<i>Not applicable</i>	-	-
		3	Clauses that do not fit into what is described above, that is, do not explain the right to revoke consent or that establish a difficult and/or non-free procedure	<withdraw3> (...) </withdraw3>	
Express consent	YES (when processing is based on consent), in view of art. 8th, § 1st, of the LGPD	1	The consent provided in writing is separated from the other contractual clauses.	<consent1> (...) </consent1>	-
		2	<i>Not applicable</i>	-	-
		3	Although present in the contract, there is no specific clause that	<consent3> (...) </consent3>	-

stands out from the others regarding the holder's consent.

1

It is the clause that specifies, in a clear, adequate and obvious way, the types of data collected for processing. Any processing of sensitive personal data should be highlighted.

<cat1> We collect information about your location when you use our services, which helps us offer features like driving directions for your weekend getaway or showtimes for movies playing near you. </cat1>

The above clause is fully informative, since it clearly specifies the category of personal data collected, i.e. the data subject location information.

2

Not applicable

-

-

3

Clauses that do not fit into the above, that is, do not provide clear information about the types of data collected and processed, providing only vague examples of what data is collected.

<cat3> Personal Data we collect may include, but is not limited to, browser and device information, data collected through automated electronic interactions and application usage data. </cat3>

The clause above fails to be fully informative since it only provides a summary of the collected data and the list is not exhaustive, as it is clear from the wording of the clause. Besides it is undoubtedly vague, unclear and not inferable in any way what types of data will be collected through automated electronic interactions and application usage data.

1

The clause that informs the origin of the personal data collected (when not collected directly by the processing agent) is completely informative. Therefore, it is necessary to highlight whether the data was from public or private sources, from which sector, industry or organization it was obtained and

<source1> For Members outside of the United States, to the extent permitted by applicable laws and with your consent where required, Airbnb and Airbnb Payments may obtain the local version of police, background or registered sex offender checks. </source1>

The above clause is fully informative since it clearly provides information about the nature of source and from which data originate.

			the location where the information was previously located.		
		2	<i>Not applicable</i>	-	-
		3	Clauses that do not fit into the above, that is, do not provide clear information about how the data was collected or only provide vague examples about the collection.	<p><source3> Advertisers, app developers, and publishers can send us information through Facebook Business Tools they use, including our social plug-ins (such as the Like button), Facebook Login, our APIs and SDKs, or the Facebook pixel. These partners provide information about your activities off Facebook - including information about your device, websites you visit, purchases you make, the ads you see, and how you use their services - whether or not you have a Facebook account or are logged into Facebook.</source3></p> <p><source3> Airbnb and Airbnb Payments may collect information, including personal information, that others provide about you when they use the Airbnb Platform and the Payment Services, or obtain information from other sources and combine that with information we collect through the Airbnb Platform and the Payment Services.</source3></p>	<p>The above clause fails to be fully informative since it is unclear the nature of sources from which personal data originates.</p> <p>The above clause fails to be fully informative since the nature of some of the mentioned sources remains unclear, i.e. what the "other sources" entails, as well as how their nature could be identified.</p>
Automated decision	YES, due to art. 20 of the LGPD and	1	The clause that indicates the use of automated decision-making and the logic involved in said	<auto1> Users in the EU have the right to object to this type of	The clause above is fully informative since it clearly specifies that it provides the data subject has the right to

the general principle of transparency (art. 6, VI, of the LGPD)		processing is completely informative, as well as the possibility and method of exercising said right.	processing; see Section II.1.1.d for more information </auto1>	object to this type of processing, and it is immediately apparent where and how this information can be accessed, i.e. the specified number of sections in the privacy policy.
	2	<i>Not applicable</i>	-	-
	3	<p>The clause that informs the existence of an automated decision, but not the logic involved in said processing, is insufficiently informative.</p> <p>The clause that does not highlight the holder's right to request a review of automated processing is also insufficiently informative.</p> <p>Finally, we consider that any clause that denies, a priori, the right to review based on commercial and industrial secrets is abusive.</p>	<p><auto3> In certain cases such incidents may lead to deactivation by means of an automated decision making process. </auto3></p> <p><auto3> Apple does not take any decisions involving the use of algorithms or profiling that significantly affects you. </auto3></p>	<p>The clause above fails to be fully informative since it does not provide either meaningful information about the logic involved in the automated decision making process, nor the significance and the envisaged consequences of such processing for the data subject.</p> <p>The above clause fails to be fully informative since it is unclear whether or not there is an automated decision making. The clause could be interpreted to imply that there is an automated decision making that however does not significantly affect the data subject. It should also be noted that, under this interpretation, also the significance and the envisaged consequences of the processing for the data subject are unclear. Such evaluation seems to remain under the sole discretionary assessment of the data controller, since the criteria on which it is based are not provided.</p>

Second block: Clauses on data processing

Consent for use	Yes	1	When consent is explicitly required.	<cuse1> This additional information will be processed based on your consent. </cuse2>	
		2	<i>Not applicable</i>		
		3	When the user consents to the terms of the privacy policy merely by using the service.	<cuse3>when you use our websites, games, game engines, and applications, you agree to our collection, use, disclosure, and transfer of information as described in this policy, so please review it carefully. </cuse3>	
“Take it or leave it” approach (Conditioning continued service provision on consent to the privacy policy)	No	1	When the clause informs the holder: (i) prominently, the provision of products or services is conditioned on the processing of personal data; and (ii) means by which you can exercise the holder’s rights listed in art. 18 of the LGPD.		
		2	When information about the conditioning of the supply of products or services to the processing of personal data does not appear prominently, or when		

			the means by which the holder may exercise the rights listed in art. 18 of the LGPD.		
		3	When information about the conditioning of the supply of products or services to the processing of personal data is not prominent and the means by which the holder may exercise the rights listed in art. 18 of the LGPD.	<p><tol3> If you do not wish to acknowledge or accept any updates to this Privacy Statement, you may cancel your use of the Netflix service. </tol3></p> <p></tol3> Our Terms cover the entire agreement between you and Signal regarding our Services. If you do not agree with our Terms, you should stop using our Services. </tol3></p>	
Policy changes	No	1	When stipulating that the holder's awareness (or at least a reading confirmation) is necessary when changes are made to privacy policies or notices.		
		2	When a new notice is provided/announced, but the holder is not required to be aware of it by reasonable means (or read confirmation).	<p><pch2>We may review this Privacy Policy from time to time. The most current version of the policy will govern our processing of your personal data and will always be at https://twitter.com/privacy. If we make a change to this policy that, in our sole discretion, is material, we will notify you via an @Twitter update or email to the email</p>	

				address associated with your account.</pch2>	
		3	When a new notice is not necessarily provided/announced and the data subject is not aware of it (or confirmed that it has been read), for example, clauses that state that it is the data subject's responsibility to check the latest version of the privacy policy.	<pch3>We might amend the Privacy Statement from time to time. If you care about your privacy, visit this page regularly and you'll know exactly where you stand.</pch3>	
Data processing of children and adolescents	Yes	1	Clauses involving the treatment of children under 12 years of age (i) through specific and prominent consent from the legal guardian; (ii) so that information about the data collected and how it is used is public; (iii) in a simple and clear way, considering the characteristics of childhood maturity; and (iv) using reasonable efforts to verify the consent of the person responsible.	<child1>Children under the age of 13, or equivalent minimum age in the relevant jurisdiction, are not permitted to create their own Apple IDs, unless their parent provided verifiable consent or as part of the child account creation process in Family Sharing or they have obtained a Managed Apple ID account (where available) through their school.</child1> <child1>For example, a parent must review the Apple ID and Family Sharing Disclosure and agree to the Consent to Apple's Collection, Use and Disclosure of Your Child's Information; and the iTunes Store Terms and Conditions, before they can begin the Apple ID account creation process for their child.</child1>	

2

Clauses in which the first three conditions above are met, but efforts to verify the consent given by the legal guardian are not adequately specified or clearly reasonable.

<child2>Our services are not directed to children, and you may not use our services if you are under the age of 13. You must also be old enough to consent to the processing of your personal data in your country (in some countries we may allow your parent or guardian to do so on your behalf). You must be at least 16 years of age to use Periscope.</child2>

Regarding the specification of efforts: the LGDP, like the GDPR, does not specify methods, being flexible in this regard. The ANPD also does not have publications on what would be appropriate methods.

Already the [FTC](#) American has a list of possible methods that states that “[a] acceptable methods include having the parent:

- sign a consent form and send it back to you via fax, mail, or electronic scan;
- use a credit card, debit card, or other online payment system that provides notification of each separate transaction to the account holder;
- call a toll-free number staffed by trained personnel;
- connect to trained personnel via a video conference;
- provide a copy of a form of government issued ID that you check against a database, as long as you delete the identification from your

records when you finish the verification process;

- [answer a series of knowledge-based challenge questions](#) that would be difficult for someone other than the relative to answer; or
- verify a picture of a driver's license or another photo ID submitted by the parent and then compare that photo to a second photo submitted by the parent, [using facial recognition technology.](#)"

The American COPPA says the same.

3

Any case other than those above.

<child3>If you are under the age of 18 and have an account for our websites, mobile apps, game engines, games, or other online services, you may request that we remove certain content that you provided, such as deleting or editing comments you have posted.</child3>

Advertising

No

1

Consent is required in line with LGPD requirements and opt-out is possible or it is stated that the

<ad1>Subject to your separate consent or where explicitly permitted under applicable laws on email marketing, Valve

			<p>data collected will not be used for marketing purposes.</p> <p>If the provision of data for marketing is a condition for providing a service, consent must be given prominently (see “Take it or leave it approach” above).</p>	<p>may send you marketing messages about products and services offered by Valve to your email address.</ad1></p>	
		2	<p>Consent is not required, but opt-out is possible.</p>	<p><ad2>You can opt-out of receiving marketing communications from us by following the unsubscribe instructions included in our marketing communications or changing your notification settings within your Airbnb Account.</ad2></p>	
		3	<p>Consent is not required and opt-out is not possible.</p>	<p><ad3>Ads and other sponsored content: We use the information we have about you including information about your interests, actions and connections-to select and personalize ads, offers and other sponsored content that we show you.</ad3></p>	
Any other type of consent	No	1	Not applicable		
		2	<p>“Hidden” consents, whether through certain expressions or</p>	<p><c2>If you provide us with your phone number, you agree to receive text messages from</p>	

			semantic structures. This type of clause is always problematic.	Twitter to that number as your country's laws allow.</c2>	
		3	Not applicable		
Any other type of clause we believe to be particularly problematic.	No	1	Not applicable		
		2	Other problematic clauses, including lawyerly instinct (for example, clauses that are unclear in their meaning or that state that responsibility for processing lies with the data subject)		
		3	Not applicable		
Use of Cookies	Yes	1	When the clause states that the processing (i) only uses session cookies or (ii) uses cookies for advertising purposes with the possibility of opt-in.	<p><cookie1> We only use first-party cookies. These cookies are used to store your login information. [...] We do not use third-party trackers/cookies for the use of this site. </cookie1></p> <p><cookie1> We do not store cookies </cookie1></p> <p><cookie1> Cookies are stored on your individual device and you have full control over their use. You may deactivate or restrict the transmission of cookies by changing the settings of your web browser. [...] Should you</p>	

visit duckduckgo.com site with cookies deactivated, you may possibly not be able to use all of the functions of our site to the full extent. You will not be able to opt-out of any cookies or other technologies that are “strictly necessary” for the functioning of our website and services.<cookie1>

2

When processing, it uses cookies for advertising purposes with the possibility of opt-out.

<cookie2> We also allow specific partners to collect information from your browser or service for advertising and measurement purposes using their own cookies or similar technologies.<cookie2>

3

When the processing (i) analyzes the holder's activities outside the service using cookies, without the holder interacting with the service, (ii) ignores “Do not track” instructions or (iii) uses cookies for advertising purposes without the possibility of opt-out.

<cookie> You can review your Off-Facebook activity, which is a summary that businesses and organizations share with us about your interactions with them, such as visiting their websites. They use our Business tools, like Facebook Pixel, to share this information with us. This helps us do things like give you a more personalized experience on Facebook. <cookie3>

<cookie3> Like many websites, we use “cookies” and other unique identifiers, and we obtain certain types of information when your web browser or

				device accesses Amazon Services and other content served by or on behalf of Amazon on other websites. <cookie3>	
Third block: Use of unclear language					
Generic expressions	Yes	1	There is no generic expression	<eg> (..) </eg1>	
		2	-	<eg> (..) </eg2>	
		3	The clause has generic expressions and its general meaning is not very precise	<eg> (..) </eg3>	
Deleted tags					
Right to petition	Note: the tag was deleted because, unlike the European context, in Brazil, there is no doubt that (i) the ANPD is the responsible authority and (ii) this right is provided for by law.	1	The clause that informs the right to petition the National Data Protection Authority is completely informative.	<complain1> You have the right to lodge a complaint with WhatsApp Ireland's lead supervisory authority, The Irish Data Protection Commissioner, or your local supervisory authority. </complain1> <complain1> If you wish to raise a concern about our use of your information (and without prejudice to any other rights you may have), you have the right to do so with your local supervisory authority or Twitter International Company's lead	The above clause is fully informative since it provides the data subject with information on the right to lodge a complaint with a supervisory authority, complying with the criteria established by the GDPR. The above clause is fully informative since it provides the data subject with information on the right to lodge a complaint with a supervisory authority, complying with the criteria established by the GDPR.

				supervisory authority, the Irish Data Protection Commission. You can find their contact details here. </complain1>	
		2	<i>Not applicable.</i>		
		3	<i>Not applicable.</i>	<complain3> You also have the right to lodge a complaint at a supervisory authority </complain3>	The above clause fails to be fully informative since it does not specify that the mentioned supervisory authority is the one located in the Member State of the data subject habitual residence, place of work or place of an alleged infringement of the GDPR or of the company's main establishment.
Holder's rights	<p>YES, based on arts. 9th, VII, and 18 of the LGPD</p> <p>Note: the tag was excluded because we considered that analyzing all rights in the same tag could generate relevant distortions regarding the unfairness of the contract.</p>	1	Clauses that list the data subject's rights and how they can take measures to exercise them.	<correct1> You can request access to your personal information, or correct or update out-of-date or inaccurate personal information we hold about you. You can most easily do this by visiting the "Account" portion of our website, where you have the ability to access and update a broad range of information about your account, including your contact information, your Netflix payment information, and various related information about your account (such as the content you have viewed and rated, and your reviews). You must be signed in to access the "Account" section. You may also request that we delete personal information that we hold about you. To make requests, or if you have any other questions regarding our privacy practices,	The above clauses are fully informative since they clearly provide the data subject with information on the rights to access, update, correct and delete personal information held by the data controller, as well as on the required steps to exercise them.

				<p>please contact our Data Protection Officer/Privacy at privacy@netflix.com. We respond to all requests we receive from individuals wishing to exercise their data protection rights in accordance with applicable data protection laws. Please also see the "Your Choices" section of this Privacy Statement for additional choices regarding your information.</p>	
		2	<i>Not applicable</i>	-	-
		3	<p>Clauses that do not fit into what is described above, that is, do not list the rights of the data subject and/or how he or she can exercise them.</p>	<p><correct3> You may access and update some of your information through your Account settings. If you have chosen to connect your Airbnb Account to a third-party application, like Facebook or Google, you can change your settings and remove permission for the app by changing your Account settings. You are responsible for keeping your personal information up-to-date.[...]You have the right to ask us to correct inaccurate or incomplete personal information concerning you (and which you cannot update yourself within your Airbnb Account).[...] In some jurisdictions, applicable law may entitle you to request copies of your personal information held by us. You may also be entitled to request copies of personal information that you have provided to us in a structured, commonly used, and machine-readable format and/or</p>	<p>The above clauses fail to be fully informative since, even though they provide a summary of what the rights involve, given the wording it is unclear under what condition data subjects can exercise their rights and how they can take steps to exercise them.</p>

				request us to transmit this information to another service provider (where technically feasible). </correct3>	
Responsibilities of processing agents	Note: the clause was deleted because we consider that the responsibilities of processing agents are already reflected inversely through the other tags	1	These are the clauses that inform, in a specific, adequate and clear way, the responsibilities of the processing agents	<resp1> (...) </resp1>	-
		2	<i>Not applicable</i>	-	-
		3	Clauses that do not fit into the above, so as not to be exhaustive and/or vague (for example, when a clause only provides examples of the responsibilities of processing agents)	<resp3> (...) </resp3>	-
Controller contact	YES, based on art. 9th, IV, of the LGPD	1	When different forms of communication with the controller are listed, such as telephone number, email and mailing address. It is important that the contact channels are appropriate to the nature of the relationship and the context of interactions between the controller and the data (example: for a virtual relationship, it is important that	<contact1> The data controller responsible for your information is Facebook Ireland, which you can contact online, or by mail at: Facebook Ireland Ltd. 4 Grand Canal Square Grand Canal Harbor Dublin 2 Ireland </contact1>	The above clause is fully informative concerning the contact details of the controller. It provides two forms of communication, i.e. an online form (there is a hyperlink under the words "contact online") and the postal address. Furthermore, the online form, that is an electronic means, is an adequate form of communication with regard to the context, the nature of relationship and interactions

			there is the possibility of virtual contact).		between the controller and the data subject.
		2	<i>Not applicable</i>	-	-
		3	Any other case that does not fit the previous one, with different forms of communication not being listed according to what the context, the nature of the relationship and the interactions between the controller and the data seem to require.	<contact3> For questions specifically about this Privacy Statement, or our use of your personal information, cookies or similar technologies, please contact our Data Protection Officer/Privacy Office by email at privacy@netflix.com . </contact3>	The clause above fails to be fully informative since it provides only one means of communication, i.e. an email address, even though it constitutes an adequate means of communication, considering the context and the nature of the relationship and interactions between the controller and the data subject . As noted above, the provided contact details should allow for different forms of communication with the data controller. Thus, it only reaches a low standard for the clarity and accessibility of the information.
Treatment hypotheses	Does NOT need to be in the terms of use	1	These are clauses that explain, among the hypotheses provided for in art. 7th of the LGPD, the legal basis for the processing. The information must be made available in a clear and appropriate way to the data subject	<basis1> The Payments Data Controller needs to collect the following information, as it is necessary for the adequate performance of the contract with you and to comply with applicable law (such as anti-money laundering regulations). </basis1> <basis1> We access, preserve and share your information with regulators, law enforcement or others: In response to a legal request, if we have a good-faith	The above clause is fully informative since it clearly describes the legal basis for the processing, i.e. the adequate performance of the contract. The above clause is fully informative since it clearly describes the legal basis for the processing, i.e. the compliance with a legal obligation to which the controller is subject.

				belief that the law requires us to do so. </basis1>	
		2	<i>Not applicable</i>		
		3	These are clauses that offer just a few examples of how the processing relates to the respective legal basis.	<basis3> We may use your information for our legitimate interests, such as to provide you with the best suitable content of the website, emails and newsletters, to improve and promote our products and services and the content on our website, and for administrative, fraud detection and legal purposes. </basis3>	The clause above fails to be fully informative since it only provides some examples of legitimate interests, which seems to be extensively applied to marketing practices and mixed with other very different purposes such as legal purposes. As a best practice and in application of the transparency principle (article 12 GDPR), legitimate interests should be clearly differentiated from other types of basis for the processing.
International data transfer	No	1	When the clause provides complete information about at least one of the following transfer mechanisms: (i) Adequacy decision (countries with adequate data protection)[at the moment, there are no ANPD regulations on the subject, but we believe that the USA, EU and Switzerland are safe bets], (ii) Global corporate standards; (iii) Explicit Consent of the Individual with specific clauses for the transfer; (iv) standard contractual clauses	<cross1>Valve complies with the EU-US Privacy Shield Framework and the Swiss-US Privacy Shield Framework as set forth by the US Department of Commerce regarding the collection, use, and retention of personal information transferred from the European Union and Switzerland to the United States. Valve has certified to the Department of Commerce that it adheres to the Privacy Shield Principles. If there is any conflict between the terms in this privacy policy and the Privacy Shield Principles, the Privacy Shield Principles shall govern. To learn more about the Privacy Shield	

			[ANPD does not have standard clauses]; (v) regularly issued seals, codes of conduct and certificates.	program, and to view our certification, please visit http://www.privacyshield.gov	
		2	When providing only a list of the transfer mechanism without specifying information that allows the user to be effectively informed.	<cross2>Apple uses approved Model Contractual Clauses for the international transfer of personal information collected in the European Economic Area and Switzerland.</cross2>	
		3	When the transfer mechanism is not informed or specified.	<cross3>Where the laws of your country allow you to do so, you authorize us to transfer, store, and use your data in the United States, Ireland, and any other country where we operate.</cross3> <cross3>In some of the countries to which we transfer personal data, the privacy and data protection laws and rules regarding when government authorities may access data may vary from those of your country.</cross3>	
Data licensing [Awaiting response from Italians - no response]	[No]	1	N/A	N/A	
		2	N/A	N/A	
		3	N/A	N/A	

Communications Confidentiality	No	1	When processing guarantees the confidentiality of messages and communications.	<msg1> Signal cannot decrypt or otherwise access the contents of your messages or calls. Signal queues end-to-end encrypted messages on its servers for delivery to devices that are temporarily offline (e.g. a phone whose battery has died). Your message history is stored on your own devices. <msg1>	Initial reasons for deletion: <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. There is no legal provision, making it a “concern” factor. 2. Maybe it's binary: what would be “only” problematic in terms of information confidentiality? Is there a “confidential (just not)”? 3. Italians have not established tags on specific data processing.
		2	[Pending]		
		3	When processing reads or processes communication data or messages for purposes other than the mere execution of the communication.	<p><msg3>We also collect the content you create, upload, or receive from others when using our services. This included things like email you write and receive, photos and videos you save, docs and spreadsheets you create, and comments you make on Youtube videos.<msg3></p> <p><msg3> Our systems automatically process content and communications you and others provide to analyze context and what's in them for the purposes described below, <msg3></p> <p><msg3> This includes your posts and comments, including saved drafts, videos you broadcast via RPAN, your messages with other users</p>	

				(e.g. private messages, chats, and modmail), and your reports and other communications with moderator and with us. <msg3>	
Transfers to third parties		1	When providing that a new consent is requested (or at least a reading confirmation) when changes are made to policies or privacy notices	<tp1>It may be necessary – by law, legal process, litigation, and/or requests from public and governmental authorities within or outside your country of residence – for Apple to disclose your personal information. </tp1>	
		2	When at least one of the following situations is observed: (i) the scope is not specified and consent is optional; (ii) the scope is specified, but consent is not optional or necessary to access the service; or (iii) the third parties are not specified.	<tp2> You can tell when a third party is involved in your transactions, and we share customer information related to those transactions with that third party. </tp2>	
		3	When the transfer object and scope are not specified, consent is required to access the service (it is not optional) and the transfer is not necessary for the performance of the contract.	<tp3>We may process your personal information for the purposes described in this Privacy Policy with your consent, for compliance with a legal obligation to which Apple is subject or when we have assessed it is necessary for the purposes of the legitimate	

				interests pursued by Apple or a third party to whom it may be necessary to disclose information.</tp3>	
Processing of sensitive personal data	No	1	When one of the legal bases specified in art. 11 of the LGPD (specific and prominent consent of the holder or their guardian for specific purposes; compliance with legal or regulatory obligation; regular exercise of rights; protection of the life or physical safety of the holder or third party; protection of health in procedures carried out by healthcare professionals or health authority; guarantee of fraud prevention and security of the holder), not necessarily direct and textual, but about its content.		
		2	Clauses that claim to be covered by one of the legal bases set out in art. 11 of the LGPD (specific and prominent consent of the holder or their guardian for specific purposes; compliance with legal or regulatory obligation; regular exercise of rights; protection of the life or physical	<sens2>To create personalized products that are unique and relevant to you, we use your connections, preferences, interests and activities based on the data we collect and learn from you and others (including any data with special protections you choose to provide where you have given your explicit consent); how you use and interact with our Products; and the	

			safety of the holder or third party; protection of health in procedures carried out by healthcare professionals or health authority; guarantee of fraud prevention and security of the holder), but present incomplete and/or non-exhaustive information (ie: do not specify the purpose)	people, places, or things you're connected to and interested in on and off our Products. </sens2>	
		3	Clauses that do not make any reference to any legal basis listed in art. 11 of the LGPD, not necessarily direct and textual, but about its content.		
Indeterminate conditioners	Yes	1	There is no conditioner	<con> (..) </ci1>	
		2	-	<con> (..) </ci2>	
		3	The clause has conditioners and its meaning is indeterminate	<con> (..) </ci3>	
Modulation	Yes	1	There is no use of non-specific adverbs and adjectives	<mo> (..) </mo1>	
		2	-	<mo> (..) </mo2>	

		3	There is use of non-specific adverbs and adjectives	<mo> (..) </mo3>	
Treatment modality	Yes	1	The clause indicates the specific methods of data processing (noting processes, means and purposes of processing)	<met> (..) </met1>	
		2	The clause is unclear regarding the processing methods, not being transparent regarding important points in the way data is processed	<met> (..) </met2>	
		3	There is no explanation about how the data is processed	<met> (..) </met3>	
Non-specific quantifiers	Yes	1	There is no use of non-specific quantifiers	<qne> (..) </qne1>	
		2	-	<qne> (..) </qne2>	
		3	There is use of quantifiers that create ambiguity regarding a certain action or activity	<qne> (..) </qne3>	

Substantial treatment information	Yes	1	The clause provides a meaningful explanation about the logic used, as well as the importance and expected consequences of the processing for the data subject.	<ist> (..) </ist1>	
		2	The clause is unclear in its information about the logic used, as well as the importance and expected consequences of the processing for the data subject.	<ist> (..) </ist2>	
		3	There is no explanation about the logic used or the consequences of the processing for the data subject	<ist> (..) </ist3>	
Conciseness	Yes	1	The clause is direct and clear in its content	<cc> (..) </cc1>	
		2	The clause could be more concise, but its content can still be understood	<cc> (..) </cc2>	
		3	The clause provides information that is not very concise and unjustifiably long texts are used,	<cc> (..) </cc3>	

			which make the meaning of the clause unclear		
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If there is any doubt as to the degree of abusiveness of a particular clause, please mark it with the “?” instead of a number and notify the team of this question.

1.3. Technical details

1. We use the *.xml format.
2. Please tag the entire sentence, eg: <use2> By using the Services, you agree to be bound by these Terms. </use2>
3. Please fill in the table in the file titled “Tagged terms” with EACH phrase you tagged, according to the model and example. From this table, we derive the grammar for soft automatic.
4. Also note the date and version of the Terms of Service marked at the beginning of the .xml file.